

Variability in floral traits influencing outcrossing among 86 selected rice varieties and breeding lines. IRRI, 1980.

variability among rice varieties with regard to the floral characteristics studied (see figure). Eleven rice cultivars possessing some desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing were identified: BG90-2, BPI 121-407, CR179-1-717,

IR46, IR2307-247-2-2-3, IR8236-B-B-572-1, IR13188-9, IR13423-10-2-3, IR17492-18-1-2-2, IR17494-32-2-1-3, and IR17494-32-3-1-1-3. These cultivars are being used in the IRRI hybrid breeding program. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Bacterial foot rot of rice

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Bacterial foot rot disease was first found infecting a few plants of IR36 in IRRI fields in 1977; its incidence has not

increased since. A similar disease was reported in Korea and in India in 1979. Although the disease may have spread fairly widely, difficulty of recognition and identification of the causal bacterium may have handicapped realization of its presence.

Previous reports indicated that the causal pathogen was bacterial. IRRI

studies indicate that the disease IS caused by bacteria quite similar to *Erwinia chrysanthemi*, which causes bacterial cornstalk rot. Isolates from both rice and maize incited typical stalk rot on both crops by cross inoculation. Their general bacteriological characteristics are also similar to those of *E. chrysanthemi*. Four colony variants, distinguished on peptone sucrose agar medium, all incited the disease on rice as well as on maize. A distinct blue pigment was produced on slices of maize stalks by the maize isolates — but not by the rice isolates — at 20°C but not at higher temperatures. The blue pigmentation may be a specific characteristic of the maize isolates different from that of the rice isolates. However, other tests, including colony morphology on crystal violet pectate medium, growth at 36°C, α-methyl glucoside and phosphatase reactions all indicated that the rice isolates from the Philippines were similar to those from Japan and Korea, and those of *E. chrysanthemi* cause cornstalk rot. Bacterial foot rot of rice is therefore similar to the foot rot of rice found in Japan. ■

Coefficient of correlation between two scoring systems and the reaction of resistant varieties in Japan to pathotypes of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the Philippines

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The coefficients of correlation between Ezuka and Horino's scale for bacterial blight resistance and that of the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) for bacterial blight were compared on infection incited by the clipping and pin-pricking inoculations. The results were highly significant.

Using the two scoring systems, 48 varieties from Japan and the Philippines classified into different varietal groups according to resistance to virulence of the bacteria were tested in the greenhouse and in the field against 4 Philippine pathotypes of *X. oryzae*. The varieties